

REPORT ON ESTABLISHED LINKS WITH SCIENTIX

[DELIVERABLE 8.4]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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2 DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

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3 CONTRIBUTORS

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4 DISCLAIMER

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5 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

5.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document is a report that brings together a collection of activities and collaborations of the ER4STEM project with the SCIENTIX community over the 3 year period of the project.

5.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES AND TASKS

Deliverable 8.4 is directly linked with Deliverable 5.3 Repository workshops, since we have carried out these workshops in collaboration with SCIENTIX and also with the other WP8 deliverables (scientific and non-scientific dissemination activities)

5.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document provides a narrative of the activities split year by year with the SCIENTIX community as the project developed. Each chapter deals with the different activities carried out year by year. The final chapter looks towards the future and what will happen next after end of the project

6 INTRODUCTION TO SCIENTIX

Scientix (<http://www.scientix.eu/>) promotes and supports a Europe-wide collaboration among STEM (science, technology, engineering and maths) teachers, education researchers, policymakers and other STEM education professionals.

Scientix was originally born at the initiative of the European Commission as a series of projects and has, since its inception, been coordinated by European Schoolnet, a Brussels-based consortium of thirty ministries of education, which is a driving factor for innovation in teaching and learning and fosters pan-European collaboration of schools and teachers.

Scientix operates an online portal which has a database of useful materials for STEM teachers. With Scientix Ambassadors (teachers who want to push STEM) in each and every country, there are several events and initiatives happening all the time that help the spreading of STEM subjects at the local level and in the local languages.

The community behind Scientix is therefore very important for ER4STEM since the stakeholders are the same and it is a great channel through which to transmit the good work done in the project. With this in mind, even at proposal writing stage (before project start) it was always an aim of ER4STEM to link up in any way possible with Scientix and its community.

7 YEAR 1 ACTIVITIES

The first year of the project focused a lot on awareness raising overall of the project with the SCIENTIX contacts and especially talking to them in order to get their insights on how to shape the work of the project in the best way possible.

7.1 PLANNING CO-OPERATION WITH SCIENTIX - JANUARY 2016

At the beginning of the project the ER4STEM partners discussed internally how best to co-operate with the SCIENTIX community. They carried out an online discussion in January 2016 in order to focus on all the different actions to be done in collaboration between the two entities over the next 3 years. The following screenshot is a summary of the activities suggested

T8.4 Scientix

Linking web-based repository to Scientix portal

Scientix workshops for disseminating knowledge of the different work packages

Scientix teachers' panel workshops during ECER

Publication of results at Scientix conferences

Submission of articles to Scientix newsletter

Submission of information about events to social media channels of Scientix

Participation at Scientix networking events

Who,
when,
where?

As can be seen, Scientix teachers' panel workshops were planned for all three issues of ECER. However, the project Scientix 2 ended around the time that ER4STEM started and its successor project Scientix 3 did not offer any workshops of that kind anymore. Consequently it was not possible to organize Scientix teachers' panel workshops. Instead, teacher workshops were organized at ECER, which were not linked with Scientix.

7.2 NETWORKING EVENT & WORKSHOP IN BRUSSELS - FEBRUARY 2016

On the 26th and 27th February 2016 projects representatives from TU Wien and PRIA attended the 10th Scientix Networking event in Brussels where they had a 10 minute presentation on both days to project managers of other related EU projects and teachers of STEM subjects and then they had a hands on workshop to find out the requirements from a teacher's perspective about robotics educational materials.

The following are some screenshots of the presentations done

Consortium

TU WIEN
AICTIN

ESI European Software Institute
Center Eastern Europe

PRIA Practical Robotics Institute Austria

CARDIFF UNIVERSITY
PRIFYSGOL CAERDYDD

acrosslimits

CERTICON

ETL
ΕΘΝΙΚΟ ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ
NTUA

Work

Development and evaluation of ER4STEM framework

Educational Robotics Workshops in six European countries with over 4000 children in three years

ECER conferences
11-15 April 2016 in Austria,
2017 in Bulgaria and 2018 in Malta

ER4STEM repository for teachers with underlying theoretical structure to collect and improve approaches

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

er4stem

Workshop

Teacher Requirements to ER4STEM Framework and repository

Robots in my class?

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

The teachers workshop focused on the following questions:

- What connections could there be between your subject(s) and robotics?
- If you could create or choose a tool to help you with your teaching, any tool that you imagine, how would it look like?
- What would be the most important features for you?

The findings can be summarised as follows:

Availability of material (robotic kits) is an issue in many schools. Suggestions:

Material exchange between schools or a physical repository with materials and lesson plans offered by a third organization.

Teacher training: There are not robotics teachers yet. STEM teachers need help with lesson plans. They are not the experts in robotics as they are the experts in their subjects. Primary school teachers are generalists; they feel like they need the experts in the classroom.

Lesson plans are not linked to the curriculum. They should be modular, linked to topics in the curriculum and age group (or cognitive capabilities and previous knowledge). Or there should be a new subject like coding that can be easily linked with robots. Lesson plans or activity descriptions are too long. There is a need for quick previews, better graphical interface to access the information needed. Video tutorials would be very helpful.

Teaching “anything” with robotics: Why use robotics to teach something else then robotics? There is a need for lesson plans or what-if concepts and guidance for teachers to understand that any topic can be taught with robotics.

Software: to control different robotic kits. Interactive materials like virtual robots that can be accessed via internet are needed.

Projects: More international projects for schools to participate

The above findings were filtered back to all the project partners and especially to the pedagogical and technical workpackages in order to take them into account in their requirements analysis of what the teacher target groups needs are.

7.3 ER4STEM ON SCIENTIX PORTAL

The ER4STEM project was also inserted and featured on the SCIENTIX portal itself. This was an important step so that even those STEM teachers that had not been personally contacted would start to get to know about our project through the SCIENTIX Channels. The following is a screenshot taken directly from the Scientix website

The screenshot shows the Scientix website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with social media icons, a language dropdown set to 'English', a 'Sign in' button, and a search bar. Below this is a main menu with categories: HOME, SCIENTIX LIVE, COMMUNITY, EVENTS, PROJECTS (highlighted in yellow), CONFERENCE, NEWS, RESOURCES, and ABOUT. The main content area features a breadcrumb trail: Home > Projects > ER4STEM, Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. The title of the page is 'ER4STEM, EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING AND MATHEMATICS'. Below the title is a 'Share this project' section. A tabbed interface shows three tabs: 'BASIC INFORMATION' (selected), 'RESEARCH INFORMATION', and 'TEACHER INFORMATION'. The 'BASIC INFORMATION' tab contains the ER4STEM logo and text describing the project's goals and activities. To the right, there is a sidebar with 'In your country' links: Observatory, Scientix Moodle, Scientix Webinars, and Scientix blog. Below these links is a call to action: 'If you know of European or national project in STEM education, please let us know.' with a 'SUBMIT PROJECT' button. At the bottom of the sidebar, there is a link to 'Read more on what Scientix offers to science education projects' and a list of 'Online meeting room' and 'Networking events'. A section for 'For project managers:' is partially visible at the bottom.

Home > Projects > ER4STEM, Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

ER4STEM, EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING AND MATHEMATICS

Share this project

BASIC INFORMATION RESEARCH INFORMATION TEACHER INFORMATION

 ER4STEM project envisions a creative and critical use of educational robotics to maintain children's curiosity in the world

ER4STEM is a three-year EU Horizon2020 project having started 1 October 2015. The project goal is to develop an open and conceptual framework that enables multiple entry-points into Educational Robotics and creative STEM (STEAM), empowering children to solve real-world problems, addressing all young learners, and providing a continuous STEM schedule.

During the project, educational robotics workshops will be held in five European countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Malta, and UK) for over 4000 children.

The European Conference on Educational Robotics **ECER** will be hosted by project partners 2016 in Austria, 2017 in Bulgaria, and 2018 in Malta.

By the end of the project an ER4STEM repository for teachers with underlying theoretical structure of the framework will be introduced in workshops for teachers and Scientix ambassadors.

In your country

- Observatory
- Scientix Moodle
- Scientix Webinars
- Scientix blog

If you know of European or national project in STEM education, please let us know.

SUBMIT PROJECT

Read more on what Scientix offers to science education projects

- Online meeting room
- Networking events

For project managers:

8 YEAR 2 ACTIVITIES

In the second year of the project we focused on working with Scientix Ambassadors and STEM teachers whilst we were building our repository and our pedagogical tools.

8.1 NETWORKING AND PREPARATION FOR REPOSITORY WORKSHOPS

The ER4STEM partners focused on the preparation for the SCIENTIX-related activities by familiarising themselves with the different ambassadors and making contacts at the local level. The different ambassadors in each country were identified also thanks to information received from Scientix itself

SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS 2016-2019

The following people have been selected as Scientix Ambassadors and members of the teachers' panel from 2016 to 2019.

Scientix Ambassadors help share Scientix activities at national level and play an active role in supporting innovation in STEM education in their countries. Their work is essential for expanding and consolidating a community whose core values reside in sharing of good classroom practice, especially in the area of STEM, and making sure that students are equipped with the skills needed to become successful adults.

Scientix Ambassadors:

- Disseminate Scientix at national level via social media and face to face presentations.
- Help the exchange of knowledge and good practices in the area of Science Education.
- Support and improve science education in general.

Find here teachers who are Scientix Ambassadors in your country

Albania - Austria - Belgium - Bosnia & Herzegovina - Bulgaria - Croatia - Cyprus - Czech Republic - Denmark - Estonia - Finland - France - Germany - Greece - Hungary - Iceland - India - Ireland - Israel - Italy - Latvia - Lithuania - Luxembourg - Malta - Mexico - Moldova - Montenegro - Netherlands - Norway - Peru - Poland - Portugal - Romania - Serbia - Slovakia - Slovenia - Spain - Sweden - The Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia - Turkey - Ukraine - United Kingdom - United States of America - Zambia - Other

In your country

- Observatory
- Scientix Moodle
- Scientix Webinars
- Scientix blog

GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF SCIENTIX AMBASSADORS AROUND THE WORLD

Once the different ambassadors were identified, these were personally contacted with an email in order to get them on board for ER4STEM and invite them to our events / portal. The generic text of the email is found below, but each partner then personalised it / translated it as required.

Dear [NAME], Ambassador to Scientix,

The ER4STEM project, Educational Robotics for STEM, aims to turn curious young children into young adults passionate about science and technology with a hands-on use case: robotics. ER4STEM involves different activities such as workshops and conferences for school students. The project also involves the creation of a repository, which can be used for obtaining and sharing educational robotics activities. We invite teachers to make use of the provided activities in the repository, give feedback on these activities, but also to share and upload their own educational robotics activities to the repository.

The European Commission pointed out the synergy with Scientix regarding the creation and sharing of activities and workshops for children as well as the repository.

We would like to establish first links. Hence, may we ask you a few questions?

- How well are you informed about the present status and opportunities of Scientix?
- Are you actively engaged in activities linked with Scientix?
- What do you know about the options provided by Scientix in the country?
- Could you connect us with teachers interested in educational robotics so we can integrate them in the project?

Best regards,

The ER4STEM Project Partners

Thanks to the replies to these emails it was possible to start planning the workshops to be held in the 3rd year of the project as a means to disseminate the finished ER4STEM repository to the Scientix community.

8.2 ACTIVITIES DURING ECER 2017 BULGARIA - APRIL 2017

In 2017 Scientix was again invited to work together with ER4STEM during the annual ECER conference.

On 23 March 2017, Pavel Varbanov and Christina Todorova from ESI CEE met with Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evgenia Sendova and Konstantin Delchev at the Institute of Mathematics and Informatics at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IMI-BAS). IMI-BAS has been nominated and elected as Bulgaria's National Contact Point of Scientix, in partnership with the Center for Creative Training. Coordinator from IMI is Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evgenia Sendova.

Pavel Varbanov and Christina Todorova presented the ER4STEM project, showed workshop videos, activity plans, presented the current state of the ER4STEM framework, generic educational curriculum as well as the ER4STEM repository on educational robotics. We discussed together how Bulgarian teachers, educators as well as Scientix ambassadors might benefit from the ER4STEM project deliverables and products and ESI CEE expressed willingness to support Bulgarian teachers in submitting activity plans within the ER4STEM repository and keep everyone updated on upcoming ER4STEM events.

ESI CEE presented as well as the upcoming conferences on educational robotics, the European Conference on Educational Robotics (ECER 2017) and the International Conference Robotics in Education (RiE 2017) that were about to take place in Sofia, Bulgaria for the first time within the period 24-28 April 2017. Assoc. Prof. Dr. Evgenia Sendova took upon herself to disseminate information about the conferences among Scientix Ambassadors in Bulgaria.

ESI CEE further continued this correspondence beyond the meeting, updating on a regular basis Scientix Ambassadors in Bulgaria about the ER4STEM project's development and events, such as the above-mentioned conferences on educational robotics in 2017, their 2018 editions, the ER4STEM

repository webinars in January 2018 and the current state of the educational robotics workshops, delivered in public general education schools in Bulgaria.

Here are is one of the promotions created for ECER 2017 Bulgaria. Further details are found in the WP3 Conferences deliverable

8.3 14TH SCIENCE PROJECTS WORKSHOP IN THE FUTURE CLASSROOM LAB - MAY 2017

During the 14th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab hosted by Scientix in Brussels from 5th-7th May 2017 and intended for Scientix Ambassadors, Wilfried Lepuschitz and Daniel Frank (both PRIA) attended for representing ER4STEM.

An overview of the project ER4STEM was given on 6th May during the morning session to all participating Scientix Ambassadors (~50 people). In the afternoon, two workshops each lasting 1,5 hours were carried out regarding the educational robotics controller Hedgehog, which was enhanced during ER4STEM within WP5. Each workshop was attended by app. 15 Scientix Ambassadors, who showed great interest in learning about such technology and finding out on how to use it for their own teaching purposes.

The results of the workshop were posted in the Scientix portal and ER4STEM was mentioned and linked - see screenshot below:

The screenshot shows the Scientix website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with social media icons (Twitter, Facebook), a language dropdown set to 'English', a 'Sign in' button, and a search bar. The main navigation menu includes: HOME, SCIENTIX LIVE, COMMUNITY, EVENTS, PROJECTS, CONFERENCE, NEWS, RESOURCES, and ABOUT. The main content area features a breadcrumb trail: Home > Scientix Live > Science Project workshop > SPW14 at FCL after. The article title is '14TH SCIENCE PROJECTS WORKSHOP IN THE FUTURE CLASSROOM LAB'. Below the title are two photographs: the top one is labeled 'pre' and shows a large group of people at a workshop; the bottom one is labeled 'post' and shows the same group holding certificates. The text of the article states: 'The 14th Science Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab, organised by Scientix and Next-Lab took place in Brussels in May 2017, from Friday 05 (starting time: 19:30) to Sunday 07 (end ~14h). This event was a special editon for ambassadors. The 30 most active Scientix ambassadors (at the time of the selection) from the existing 358 ambassadors and 16 Next-Lab ambassadors that will be helping bring the Go-Lab ecosystem to schools throughout Europe, attended the event. ER4STEM, EDU-ARTIC and ERIS projects were also present and run excellent workshops. In total 61 participants from over 23 countries joined the event.' On the right side of the page, there is a sidebar with the heading 'In your country' and a list of links: Observatory, Scientix Moodle, Scientix Webinars, and Scientix blog. Below this is a section for 'ALL EVENTS' with a date filter for 'August, 2018' and two event listings: 'GHO 2018 and GTTP Workshop' (13.08 - 18.08 | Austria) and 'International Conference of Interdisciplinary STEM Studies 2018' (28.08 | Slovakia). A 'View All' link is at the bottom of the sidebar.

Moreover we have promoted the event also on social media through Facebook - see post below from one of our partners PRIA

9 YEAR 3 ACTIVITIES

The focus of the 3rd year collaboration with Scientix was the organisation of the webinars/online workshops for the Scientix ambassadors, teachers and wider community together with a final push for dissemination also in the Scientix Conference.

9.1 REPOSITORY WEBINARS - JANUARY 2018

A lot of effort from all the partners went in the preparation and execution of 2 online Scientix webinars on 16th and 22nd January 2018. A full report on this can be found in deliverable D5.3 Report of the Repository Workshops.

Some highlights are pasted below for completeness sake like the Agenda, a screenshot of the presentation delivered and the social media buzz created for the events.

The feedback and analysis from the webinars can also be found in deliverable D5.3

ER4STEM - Repository Workshop (Webinar) 16th January 2017 - 4:00pm - 5:00pm - CET or 22nd January 2017 - 4:00pm - 5:00pm - CET	
AGENDA	
Overall Moderator: Christina Todorova - ESICEE (Bulgaria)	
4:00pm - 4:05pm	Welcome to the webinar Ms. Angele Giuliano - AcrossLimits (Malta)
4:05pm - 4:10pm	What is ER4STEM? Ms. Angele Giuliano - AcrossLimits (Malta)
4:10pm - 4:15min	The ER4STEM Activity plans Dr. Nikoleta Yiannoutsou - UoA (Greece)
4:15pm - 4:18pm	The ER4STEM Framework Dr. Carina Girvan - Cardiff University (United Kingdom)
4:18pm - 4:20pm	The link between the framework and the repository (Ontology) Dr. Julian Angel-Fernandez - TU Wien (Austria)
4:20pm - 4:25pm	The Repository Annalise Duca - AcrossLimits (Malta)
4:25pm - 4:40pm	Hands-on using the repository Annalise Duca - AcrossLimits (Malta)
4:40pm - 4:45pm	Question and Answer Session
4:45pm - 4:50pm	Next steps and Events Wilfried Lepuschitz - PRIA (Austria)

9.2 SCIENTIX CONFERENCE BRUSSELS - MAY 2018

ER4STEM was present during the 3rd Scientix conference, that took place in Brussels, Belgium, from 4 to 6 May, 2018. During this conference, ER4STEM’s team had a 3 minutes spotlight to invite participants to come to the booth for more information. A total of 110 were given to participants, who passed, and there were one to one conversation with 30 participants, who showed interest in the project and the main results.

Stickers and fliers created and delivered during the conference.

CONSORTIUM

Vienna University of Technology (TU Wien) www.tuwien.ac.at | Austria

European Software Institute - Center Eastern Europe (ESI CEE) www.esicenter.bg | Bulgaria

Practical Robotics Institute Austria (PRIA) www.pria.at | Austria

University of Athens Educational Technology Lab (UoA) www.etl.ppp.uoa.gr | Greece

AcrossLimits www.acrosslimits.com | Malta

Cardiff University School of Social Sciences (CU) www.cardiff.ac.uk | United Kingdom

Certicon www.certicon.cz | Czech Republic

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www.twitter.com/er4stem

EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS

4 SCIENCE
TECHNOLOGY
ENGINEERING
MATHEMATICS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 665972

Dr. Julian Angel-Fernandez (above) from TU Wien presented the project and our work under the spotlight whilst below is the ER4STEM Booth at the Scientix Conference .

10 CONCLUSIONS AND LOOKING FORWARD

At the end of the project, the ER4STEM partners are satisfied with the close collaboration that was forged with Scientix during the 3 years of the project, and as part of its future sustainability goals, it aims to continue to keep this collaboration alive by participation and involvement in common events, platforms and activities.

From the Scientix point of view, it is also beneficial to have close ties with projects such as ER4STEM since it gives a focused push to one of the domains under STEM and provides the whole community with important expertise - in this case on educational robotics.

11 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for STEM
SCIENTIX	The community for science education in Europe
WP	Workpackage
SPW	Science Project Workshop
EUN	European Schoolnet

